

Synthesis and spectral studies of transition metal complexes with dibenzo-[*b,i*]-8,10,19,21-tetramethyl-[1,5,8,12]-tetraazatetradeca-1,3,5,7,10,12,14,16,18,21-decene a fourteen membered tetradentate macrocyclic ligand

Sulekh Chandra* and Sangeeta Sharma

Department of Chemistry, Zakir Husain College, University of Delhi, J. L. N. Marg, New Delhi-110 002, India

E-mail : schandra_00@yahoo.com; mrs.sangeetasharma@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : Complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}, Ru^{III} and Ir^{III} with a fourteen membered macrocyclic ligand have been synthesized. These complexes are characterized by magnetic moment, infrared, electronic and EPR spectral studies. All of complexes were found to have six-coordinate octahedral geometry and are of the high-spin type except the Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complex which is four-coordinate, square-planar and diamagnetic.

Keywords : Macrocyclic compounds, transition metal ions, spectral studies.

The complexes of metal ions with synthetic macrocyclic ligands are significant because of their resemblance with many natural systems e.g. porphyrins and cobalamines. The chemical properties of macrocyclic complexes can be tuned to force metal ions to adopt unusual coordination geometry. Transition metal macrocyclic complexes have received much attention as a active part of metalloenzymes¹ as biomimic model compounds² due to its resemblance with natural proteins like hemerythrin and enzymes. A number of reviews³⁻⁹ have been published on the general biochemistry of copper, electronic aspects of active sites^{10,11} and relevant model chemistry of simple copper complexes^{12,13}. Platinum complexes act as anticancer agents by interacting with DNA. Binding to DNA was studied by Roberts *et al.*¹⁴. In the present paper we report the synthesis and characterization of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}, Ru^{III} and Ir^{III} complexes of macrocyclic ligand dibenzo-[*b,i*]-8,10,19,21-tetramethyl-[1,5,8,12]-tetraazatetradeca-1,3,5,7,10,12,14,16,18,21-decene [AOP].

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade, and were procured from Aldrich. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received. All solvents used were of standard/spectroscopic grade.

Synthesis of complexes :

A template reaction was carried out for the formation

of the complexes. A hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of the metal salt (0.025 mol) was mixed with a hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.05 mol) and with an ethanolic solution (20 mL) of acetylacetone (0.05 mol) in the presence of a few drops of conc. HCl. The solution was refluxed for about four to five hours in each case. The complexes precipitate out on cooling the reaction mixture overnight. They were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over P₄O₁₀, yield 49-68%.

Physical measurements :

Microanalysis (C, H and N) of these complexes were carried out on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 instrument as Nujol mulls [for 1 and 7] and KBr pellets [for 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9 and 10]. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMF solution on a Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. The molar conductance was measured on a Elico conductivity bridge (type CM₈2T).

Magnetic susceptibility measurements (Gouy-balance) were made at room temperature using CuSO₄·5H₂O as calibrant. EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as powdered samples at room temperature on an E-4 EPR spectrometer using DPPH as the *g*-marker. The molecular weights of complexes were determined cryoscopically in benzene.

Results and discussion

The analytical and molar conductance (Table 1) val-

Table 1. Molar conductance and elemental analysis of the complexes

Sl. no.	Complex and empirical formula	Molar conductance ^a ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Colour	Yield (%)	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
						M	C	N	H
1.	Cr(AOP)Cl ₃	81.3	Green	68	232	9.98	52.04	10.98	4.01
	(10.34)					(52.53)	(11.14)	(4.77)	
2.	Mn(AOP)Cl ₂	10.4	Brown	60	235	11.86	55.67	4.91	10.79
	(11.69)					(56.17)	(5.10)	(11.91)	
3.	Fe(AOP)Cl ₃	109	Brownish	55	235	11.89	52.15	11.03	4.39
	black		(11.02)			(52.14)	(11.06)	(4.74)	
4.	Co(AOP)Cl ₂	12.3	Brown	63	243	11.98	54.76	11.01	4.93
	(12.43)					(55.70)	(11.81)	(5.06)	
5.	Ni(AOP)Cl ₂	8.2	Dark	49	238	12.65	54.91	10.86	4.72
	brown		(12.39)			(55.73)	(11.82)	(5.07)	
6.	Cu(AOP)Cl ₂	14.8	Black	65	240	12.78	55.74	10.98	4.77
	(13.28)					(55.17)	(11.70)	(5.02)	
7.	Ru(AOP)Cl ₃	83.8	Black	55	250	18.13	47.96	10.01	4.02
	(18.31)					(47.87)	(10.15)	(4.35)	
8.	Pd(AOP)Cl ₂	246	Dark	60	246	20.24	50.03	10.05	4.01
	brown		(20.35)			(50.67)	(10.75)	(4.61)	
9.	Pt(AOP)Cl ₂	253	Black	65	254	31.11	42.85	8.91	3.44
	(31.97)					(43.28)	(9.18)	(3.93)	
10.	Ir(AOP)Cl ₃	118	Black	55	246	28.84	40.16	8.00	2.97
	(29.88)					(41.09)	(8.72)	(3.74)	

^aSolvent used for molar conductance : DMF.

ues of all the complexes in DMF solution suggest that general formulas of the complexes are $[\text{MLCl}_2]$ [where $\text{M} = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{L} = \text{AOP}$], $[\text{M}'\text{LCl}_2]\text{Cl}$ [where $\text{M}' = \text{Cr}^{\text{III}}, \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}, \text{Ru}^{\text{III}}$ and Ir^{III}], $[\text{PdL}]\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{PtL}]\text{Cl}_2$. In the IR spectrum of the ligand the absence of absorption around 3400 cm^{-1} shows that the free amino groups are not there. No band is observed around $1700\text{--}1800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which indicates the elimination of water molecule in the ligand. The characteristic bands due to chelated ligand appear to $1500\text{--}1700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups present in the ligand is indicated by bands at 1375 and $1425\text{--}1435 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The position of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band¹⁵ (1620 cm^{-1}) is shifted to lower side in the complex indicate that the coordination takes place through the nitrogen of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ group. Hence, the ligand is tetradentate. Phenyl group shows the absorption in the range $700\text{--}780$ and $1400\text{--}1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band appearing around 450 cm^{-1} in all the complexes indicate $\nu_{\text{M}=\text{N}}$ vibration which further confirms the coordination of these groups with metal ions.

The magnetic moment (3.76 B.M.) at room tempera-

ture of the Cr^{III} complexes lies within the range expected for high-spin octahedral Cr^{III} complexes. The electronic spectrum of the complex recorded in DMF displays four bands at 18500 , 22650 , 25100 and 29100 cm^{-1} . Six-coordinate complexes with O_h symmetry show three spin-allowed bands¹⁶ of which the highest energy band assignable to the ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition occur around 30000 cm^{-1} . The spectrum of the complex under study shows four bands below 30000 cm^{-1} , which cannot be interpreted in terms of idealized symmetry elements in the complexes. Such six-coordinated chromium(III) complexes can have either C_{4v} or D_{4h} symmetry. In the present complex, the four transitions observed may be assigned to ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g^a(\nu_1)$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{2g}(\nu_2)$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(\nu_3)$ and ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g^b(\nu_4)$ transitions arising from the lifting of the degeneracy of the orbital triplet (in octahedral symmetry) in order of increasing energy and assuming D_{4h} symmetry around the metal ion. In O_h symmetry, ν_1 and ν_2 are derived from the ${}^4T_{2g}$ level, whilst ν_3 and ν_4 from ${}^4T_{1g}(F)$. The C_{4v} symmetry has been ruled out because of the greater splitting of the first band and lower intensity of spectral bands. On the basis of symmetry argu-

Table 2. Ligand field parameters of the complexes

Complex	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	B	C (cm^{-1})	Z	LFSE (kJ mol^{-1})	g	F_4	F_2	hx
Cr(AOP)Cl ₃	1850	373	0.40	1491	0.69	265.6	1.93	-	-	-
Mn(AOP)Cl ₂	1820	700	0.89	3560	-	-	1.981	104	1221	1.57
Co(AOP)Cl ₂	1018	1061	0.94	-	-	218.9	-	-	-	-
Ni(AOP)Cl ₂	1080	600	0.58	2400	-	154.8	-	-	-	-

ments Lever *et al.*¹⁷ have devised a normalized spherical harmonic Hamiltonian (NSH) theory applicable to molecule of D_{4h} . The newly developed NSH theory relates the classical ligand field parameters to NSH absolute ligand field parameters. For our complex the NSH parameters are $D_t = 474$, $D_s = 2413$, $D_g = 16890$, $DT = 6403$, $DQ = 54472$ and $DT/DQ = 0.117$ (Table 2). DQ is a measure of the average ligand field experienced by the metal ion unlike the classical Dq , which is the measure of the in-plane ligand field. The DT/DQ ratio provides the amount of distortion of the molecule. The value of DT/DQ is 0.117 and thus indicates that the complex is moderately distorted. The EPR spectrum of the complex has been recorded as a polycrystalline sample at room temperature. The g -value is found to be 1.93. The g -value was calculated using the experience, $g = 2.0023[1 - (4\lambda/10DQ)]$ where λ is the spin-orbit coupling constant for the metal ion in the complex. It was noted that the reduction of the spin-orbit coupling constant from the free ion value of 90 cm^{-1} for chromium(III) may be employed as a measure of metal ligand covalency. It is possible to derive a covalency parameter λ , analogous to the nephelauxetic parameter which is the ratio of the spin-orbit coupling constant for the complex and the free Cr^{III} ion. This also indicates appreciable covalent character in the complex.

Manganese(II) complex shows a magnetic moment corresponding to five unpaired electrons i.e. 5.95 B.M. which indicates that Mn^{II} is high-spin in this case. The electronic spectrum of the complex displays weak absorption bands at 18200, 24800, 29700 and 31900 cm^{-1} characteristic of octahedral geometry¹⁸. These bands may be assigned to

transitions respectively. Higher values of extinction coefficient may be due to lower symmetry or mixing of charge-transfer. The value for the ligand field parameters have been calculated ($Dq = 1820 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.89$ and $C = 3560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The value of Dq could be

evaluated with the help of the curve transition energies vs Dq by Orgel¹⁹ using the energy due to the transition ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4G)$. Parameters B and C were calculated by using the methods reported earlier^{20,21}. The calculated value of β indicates that the complex under study has covalent character. The EPR spectrum of the complex has been recorded as polycrystalline sample and in DMF solution. The polycrystalline sample gives one broad isotropic signal centered at approximately the free electron g -value ($g_0 = 2.0023$). The broadening of the spectrum probably is due to spin relaxation²². In DMF solution the complex gives an EPR spectrum containing six lines arising due to hyperfine interaction^{23,24} between the unpaired electrons with the Mn nucleus ($I = 5/2$). The nuclear magnetic quantum number, M_I corresponding to the lines are $-5/2, -3/2, -1/2, +3/2, +5/2$ from low to high field.

The iron(III) complex was found to have the composition $[\text{FeLCl}_3]$ where L is the ligand. This complex shows a magnetic moment corresponding to five unpaired electrons (i.e. 5.95 B.M.) indicating the presence of high-spin Fe^{III} ion. The electronic spectrum of this complex shows three spectral bands at 16800 (ν_1), 20500 (ν_2) and 25900 cm^{-1} (ν_3) which are characteristic of octahedral geometry. The Mössbauer spectral values [isomer shift = 0.6323 mm s^{-1} at 300 K and quadruple splitting value = 1.1305 mm s^{-1}] indicates that the iron exist in +3 oxidation state and have distorted octahedral geometry with four nitrogen and two chlorine atom surrounding it.

The magnetic moment (5.05 B.M.) of the cobalt(II) complex lies within the range expected for high-spin octahedral Co^{II} complexes¹⁸. The electronic spectrum exhibit a broad band at ca. 8700 cm^{-1} and two shoulders at 14000 and 20500 cm^{-1} on the rising charge-transfer band tentatively assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g} (\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P) (\nu_3)$ transitions respectively. The low value of $\nu_2/\nu_1 = (1.61)$ may be due to distortion of the octahedral structure^{18,25}. This is consistent with very broad nature of the ν_1 band which may be assigned to the envelope of the transitions from ${}^4E_g ({}^4T_{1g})$ to the components ${}^4B_{2g}$ and 4E_g of ${}^4T_{2g}$ characteristic of tet-

ragonally-distorted octahedral environment. The EPR spectrum of the complex under study was recorded at liquid nitrogen temperature because the rapid spin lattice relaxation of Co^{II} broadened the lines at higher temperature ($g_{\parallel} = 5.354$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.617$). The large deviation of the g -values from the spin only value ($g = 2.0023$) is due to large angular momentum contribution.

Nickel(II) complex shows a magnetic moment (3.00 B.M.) corresponding to two unpaired electrons. The electronic spectrum of the nickel complex shows two well defined bands at 10800 and 16700 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) transitions respectively. Here splitting of the ν_1 band is not observed which is generally observed in D_{4h} symmetry. So D_1 , D_q^E and D_q^A cannot be calculated. The third $d-d$ transition band (ν_3) which may be obscured by the more intense charge-transfer band, is calculated to be at 25000 cm^{-1} . The value of ν_2/ν_1 is 1.55 and the ligand field parameters Dq , B and β have been found¹⁸ to be 1080, 600 and 0.58 respectively. All of these values, together with the magnetic moment (3.00 B.M.) are characteristic of an octahedral geometry for this complex. The complex is found to be paramagnetic high-spin and octahedral.

Copper(II) complex was found to be 1.90 B.M. The electronic spectrum of complex displays two bands at 13700 and 18600 cm^{-1} . The electronic spectrum of six-coordinate Cu^{II} complex have either D_{4h} or C_{4v} symmetry and the E_g and T_{2g} levels of the 2D free ion will split into B_{1g} , A_{1g} , B_{2g} and E_g levels, respectively. Thus, three-spin allowed transition are expected in the visible or near IR region but only few complexes are known, in which such bands are resolved either by "Gaussian analysis" or by "Single crystal polarization" studies²⁵. These bands have been assigned to the following transitions, in order of increasing energy ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \leftarrow d_{z^2}$), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \leftarrow d_{xy}$) and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \leftarrow d_{xz,yz}$). The energy level sequence will depends on the amount of tetragonal distortion due to ligand field and John-Teller effects²⁶⁻²⁸. The electronic spectrum of the complex shows bands at 13700 cm^{-1} and a well defined shoulder at 13700–18600 cm^{-1} . These may be assigned to the ${}^2B_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions respectively. The EPR spectrum²³⁻²⁵ of the present complex exhibit a well resolved anisotropic signals in the parallel and perpendicular ${}^{63}\text{Cu}$ region. The observed data show that $g_{\parallel} = 2.2615$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.0555$ and the g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values are closer to 2 and $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. This suggest major distortion in the copper(II) complex from O_h symmetry i.e. D_{4h} symmetry.

Palladium(II) complex is diamagnetic as expected for

a low-spin d^8 system. The low-spin square-planar metal complexes are characterized by three spin allowed $d-d$ bands, corresponding to the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_g$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ transitions, respectively. The complex under study display two bands at 22950 and 32450 cm^{-1} respectively. These bands may be assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ (ν_1) and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ (ν_2) transitions respectively. The charge-transfer band display at 37735 cm^{-1} .

The iridium(III) complex is diamagnetic as expected for a low-spin type. Electronic spectrum of the complex positively affirm an octahedral configuration around the central metal ion. The electronic spectral band appears at 17650 and 23300 cm^{-1} and a band appear at 37500 cm^{-1} . The bands may be assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ transitions in increasing order of energy. The band at 37500 cm^{-1} may be assigned to charge-transfer band.

The Ru³⁺ complex shows magnetic moment 1.71 B.M. at room temperature, which is lower than the spin only value. The lowering in μ_{eff} value may arise due to effect of ligand field, metal/metal interaction or considerable electron delocalization. Electronic spectra of the complex positively shows an octahedral configuration around the central metal ion. The electronic spectral bands appear at 13800, 17300, 25125 cm^{-1} and a few band above 30000 cm^{-1} in Ru³⁺ complexes. The bands may be assigned to ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$, transition in increasing energy. The bands above 30000 cm^{-1} may be assigned to charge-transfer band.

The ligand field parameters Δ , B and β have been calculated for the complex using the following equation.

$$\nu_1 = \Delta - 4B + 86(B)^2/\Delta$$

$$\nu_2 = \Delta + 12B + 2(B)^2/\Delta$$

The values of Δ , B , β and ν_1/ν_2 are zero, 494 cm^{-1} , 0.79 and 1.25.

The value of β indicates that there is no considerable orbital overlap with strong covalency in the metal ligand σ bond.

The magnetic moment of the platinum(II) complex prove to be diamagnetic, indicative of the square/planar geometry. The electronic spectra of the complex positively affirm the presence of square/planar geometry of the complex. Three $d-d$ spin/allowed transition are expected corresponding to the transitions from three lower lying "d" levels to the empty $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. The ground state is ${}^1A_{2g}$ and the excited states corresponding to these transition are ${}^1A_{2g}$, ${}^1B_{1g}$ and 1E_g in increasing order of energy. The electronic spectral band appeared at 24550 and 29400 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transi-

tion and charge-transfer band.

On the basis of above discussion the following structures may be proposed for the complexes.

$n = 0$ for Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}; $n = 1$ for Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ru^{III} and Ir^{III}.

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References

1. A. Chaudhary, S. Dave, R. Swaroop and R. V. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 371.
2. S. Chandra, L. K. Gupta and K. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 833.
3. T. G. Spiro (ed.), "Metal Ions in Biology", Vol. 13, Wiley, New York, 1981.
4. H. Sigel (ed.), "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", Vol. 13, Dekker, New York, 1981.
5. J. A. Fee, *Struct. Bond (Bed)*, 1975, **1**, 23.
6. CIBA Foundation Symposium no. 79, *excerpta medica*, Amsterdam, 1980.

7. H. Beinert, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **33**, 55.
8. B. Reinhammer, *Adv. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1979, **1**, 91.
9. S. H. Laurie and E. S. Mohammed, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **3**, 279.
10. E. I. Solomon, K. W. Penfield and D. E. Wilcore, *Struct. Bond. (Berl)*, 1983, **1**, 53.
11. H. B. Gray, E. I. Solomon and T. G. Spiro (ed.), "Metal Ions in Biology", Wiley, New York, 1981, Ch. 1, p. 3.
12. H. Sigel (ed.), "Metal Ions in Biological System", Vol. 12, Dekker, New York, 1980.
13. E. Ulrich and J. L. Markley, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1978, **27**, 109.
14. J. J. Roberts and A. J. Thomson, *Prog. Nucleic Acid, Res. Mol. Biol.*, 1979, **22**, 71.
15. C. R. K. Rao and P. S. Zacharias, *Polyhedron*, 1997, **16**, 1201.
16. J. R. Perumareddi, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 73.
17. J. C. Doinini, B. R. Hollebhone and A. B. P. Lever, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **22**, 225.
18. A. B. P. Lever, "Crystal Fields Spectra. In Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 1st ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, pp. 249-360.
19. L. E. Orgel, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1955, **23**, 1004.
20. S. Chandra, K. B. Pandeya and R. P. Singh, *Gazz. Chem. Ital.*, 1980, **110**, 207.
21. S. Chandra, *Acta Chim. Scand.*, 1982, **111**, 155.
22. D. M. Hong, H. H. Wei, L. L. Gan, G. H. Lee and Y. Wang, *Polyhedron*, 1996, **15**, 2335.
23. R. Rajan, R. Rajaram, B. U. Nair, T. Ramasami and T. Mandal, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1996, 2019.
24. S. Chandra and Y. Kumar, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Bangalore)*, 1983, **92**, 249.
25. B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **37**, 37.
26. I. M. Proceter, B. J. Hathaway and P. Nicholls, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1678.
27. A. A. G. Tomilinson, R. J. Hathaway, D. E. Billing and P. Nicholls, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1965, 65.
28. S. N. Choi, E. R. Menzel and J. R. Wasson, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 417.